

Impact of the Expansion of the Universe on Tract Information Processing

Aman Chawla

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Abstract

In this paper, the author presents an outline of a computation that will enable an understanding of the conception of the universe in different eras.

The universe is conceivable by the human brain, not just in imagination. States of awareness have been reported in the mystical literature of the world throughout times immemorial which testify to this. In this paper we propose a derivation of the exact impact of the expanding universe on classical and quantum axon tract information processing. By plugging in and studying the derived result at different times, one can thereby acquire a scientific picture of how the conception of the universe would have been, had brains been around in those various eras of universal history.

The outline is as follows. We use Weinberg's exposition on cosmology [1]. Equations (1.1.11) and (1.2.1) describe how the metric would change with time in an expanding universe. The metric defines how distances are computed in general relativity. This specifies the distance between any two points. In a simplified picture, we take this time-varying two-point relation and use it to rederive the three-dimensional tract action potential propagation equations from [2]¹. Computer simulations can then be used to study the 'expansion' frequency response of the tract [3]. Thus, if the brain is used as a probe and placed in different time eras, we can use the derived formulae to understand the then-present temporal information signaling in the brain. In combination with [4], this would yield how 'subjects' would see 'objects' at those times.

In this paper we have outlined a way to conceive the conception of the universe in different periods of its evolution. Instead of the universe as a vast formless entity being conceived by a convoluted ('sulci-' and 'gyri-' endowed) system, we have turned the tables and enabled man to get a conception of total cosmic history. This represents a novel view and opens up further investigations. For example, temporal slice pictures from various eras and various positions may be obtained and one can perhaps use some form of the Shannon-Nyquist sampling theorem [5] to determine whether those are sufficient to put together

¹This development is carried out in Appendix 1.

a picture of the whole cosmos at all times. This reduces the universe to a signal in a very literal sense. Investigations such as those on the wave function of the universe [6] can be seen perhaps in a new light [7] as well. It may also be a way to combine the ‘many’ worlds of Everett [8] into one.

Appendix 1

From Equation (35.12) of [9] we have,

$$\frac{D^2 n^j}{d\tau^2} = -R_{j0k0} n^k \quad (1)$$

and

$$n^j = x_B^j. \quad (2)$$

Further,

$$R_{ij} = g^{kl} R_{kilj}. \quad (3)$$

If we assume an Einstein space is being considered, then

$$R_{ij} = \Lambda g_{ij} \quad (4)$$

where Λ is a constant of proportionality. Thus,

$$R_{kilj} = \frac{\Lambda}{n-1} (g_{ik} g_{jl} - g_{il} g_{jk}). \quad (5)$$

Note that \tilde{g}_{ij} , the spatial part of g_{ij} , is given by

$$\tilde{g}_{ij} = \frac{R_{ij}}{-[2K + 2\dot{a}^2 + a\ddot{a}]} \quad (6)$$

based on Equation (1.5.13) of [1]. In the ADM formalism,

$$g_{ij} = \begin{pmatrix} -N^2 + N_i N^i & N_j \\ N_i & \tilde{g}_{ij} \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

where N is the assumed ‘lapse’ function. Finally,

$$\frac{d^2 x_B^{\hat{j}}}{d\tau^2} = -R_{j0k0} x_B^{\hat{k}} \quad (8)$$

which can be integrated to get the variation of distance with time as the universe expands. Following next a similar development as in [3], we can then perform simulations in MATLAB.

References

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